

Index Page

SBP:	2–8
DBP:	9–15
P_TNF_Alpha:	16–22
P_IL6:	23–29
P_ALAT:	30–36
P_GT:	37–43
P_uric_acid:	44–50
P_Prot_carb:	51–57
B_GSSG:	58–64
B_GSH:	65–71
GSSG_GSH_ratio:	72–78
LPO:	79–85
MDA:	86–92
P_gluc_fast:	93–99
S_ins_fast:	100–106
HOMA_IR_fast:	107–113
P_TG_fast:	114–120
P_tot_chol_fast:	121–127
P_HDL_chol_fast:	128–134
P_LDL_chol_fast:	135–141
P_HMW_adiponectin:	142–148
P_leptin:	149–155
P_leptin_receptor:	156–162
S_IGF1:	163–169
P_irisin:	170–176

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity

Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers

Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity

High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF, log₁₀ scaled)

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: SBP&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: DBP&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TNF_Alpha&CO_7dayrolling

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_IL6&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_ALAT&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_GT&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&PM10_7dayrolling

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_uric_acid&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_Prot_carb&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSSG&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: B_GSH&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: GSSG_GSH_ratio&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: LPO&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: MDA&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_gluc_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_ins_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: HOMA_IR_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_TG_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_tot_chol_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HDL_chol_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_LDL_chol_fast&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_HMW_adiponectin&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF, log₁₀ scaled)

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF, \log_{10} scaled)

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF, \log_{10} scaled)

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF, log₁₀ scaled)

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_leptin_receptor&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: S_IGF1&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&NO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&NO2_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&NOx_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&PM10_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&PM2.5_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&O3_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

Diagnostics for Model: P_irisin&CO_7dayrolling

Heteroscedasticity
Reference line should be flat and horizontal

Outliers
Points should be inside the contour lines

Collinearity
High collinearity (VIF) may inflate parameter uncertainty

Normality of Residuals

Autocorrelation of Residuals

Random effects distribution

